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**MOVING TOWARDS
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FOR EUROPE**

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**SECOND
INTERNATIONAL
CONFERENCE
ON AIR POLLUTION**

**SECOND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON AIR
POLLUTION –
MOVING TOWARDS CLEAN AIR FOR EUROPE**

PROGRAMME
AND
BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

virtual conference
25-26 September 2024

Dear Participants,
Dear Colleagues,

We proudly announced the “Second International Conference on Air Pollution – Moving Towards Clean Air for Europe”. This conference is organized in the framework of the LIFE IP HungAIRy coordinated by HungaroMet Hungarian Meteorological Service. Our goal is to bring together experts, decision makers and other relevant stakeholders from across Europe to discuss key air pollution issues. Air pollution remains the largest environmental health risk in Europe and significantly impacts the global climate. While substantial efforts have been made to reduce concentrations of key pollutants, further reductions in emissions across various sectors are essential to meet the required standards and guidelines. With participants and presenters from countries including Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Ireland, Poland, Serbia, and Slovakia, the conference will be a truly international event, offering an excellent opportunity to exchange knowledge and explore diverse perspectives.

The topics to be discussed include, but are not limited to:

- air quality modelling,
- new technologies and networks in air quality monitoring,
- emission reduction strategies and practices in different sectors (e.g. residential, traffic, agriculture),
- monitoring the impact of activities,
- communication strategies and good practices,
- policy uptake,
- effects of air pollution on the health, climate and the built environment.

The conference will feature presentations from both ongoing and recently completed projects, particularly those funded under the European Union’s LIFE program, along with contributions from experts involved in international projects funded by other programs, such as Horizon 2020.

We are looking forward to meeting you online on 25-26 September 2024!

The HungAIRy LIFE IP team

Impact of nitrogen dioxide exposure on the risk of severe acute exacerbations in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease

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Abstract:

Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) can impair antioxidant defenses in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) patients, leading to increased airway inflammation and bronchial reactivity, which may exacerbate COPD. This study evaluated the impact of rising NO₂ concentrations on severe acute exacerbations of COPD (AE-COPD) of non-infectious origin. Over five years (2017-2022), average daily NO₂ concentrations from monitoring stations in Novi Sad, Serbia, and daily hospitalizations for severe AE-COPD at the Institute for Pulmonary Diseases of Vojvodina were analyzed. Quasi-Poisson generalized linear models and distributed lag nonlinear models (DLNM) calculated the relative risk of severe AE-COPD per 10 µg/m³ increase in NO₂. During the study, there were 552 hospitalizations for severe non-infectious AE-COPD, with an average daily NO₂ concentration of 14.54 µg/m³ (range 1.82-78.00 µg/m³). For the overall sample, each 10 µg/m³ increase in NO₂ was associated with a cumulative relative risk (RR) over eight days of 0.67 (95% CI 0.33-1.37) for AE-COPD hospitalization, which was not statistically significant. However, significant effects were observed for women (RR 2.55, 95% CI 1.50-4.31) and men (RR 1.94, 95% CI 1.04-3.62). Age-specific effects were also notable: RR for individuals under 65 years was 2.19 (95% CI 1.05-4.59) and for those 65 years or older, 2.37 (95% CI 1.45-3.89). When adjusting for other pollutants (PM_{2.5} and SO₂) and meteorological factors (temperature and humidity), these effects lost significance. The study suggests that increased NO₂ concentrations are linked to a higher risk of severe AE-COPD in both genders and across age groups. However, these associations may be confounded by other environmental factors. The findings highlight the need for policies to reduce NO₂ emissions and improve air quality to protect respiratory health and reduce severe COPD exacerbations. Further research is needed to clarify these relationships and enhance strategies for mitigating air pollution's impact on respiratory diseases.